

REINFORCING

The European platform for
Open and Responsible Research and
Innovation practices

REINFORCING aims to become the EU Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) **central point of knowledge and expertise** that supports **territories and institutions** in implementing ORRI activities. This will be achieved through the One-Stop Source platform.

The One-Stop Source provides you with:

Grants

Financial support through **7 open calls** to fund organizations that are newcomers wishing to embark on ORRI and experienced entities looking for strengthening ORRI implementation.

ORRI Community

REINFORCING's ORRI Community will bring together **experienced organizations and facilitators** who have had their own ORRI journeys and can share their experiences.

Tools

Useful resources and best practices to inspire and **help institutions** in designing and implementing their ORRI actions.

Training

Training opportunities delivered by experienced experts about **specific ORRI needs** emerging from the interaction with the community.

Pathways

Specific guidance fitting concrete **ORRI challenges** to improve ORRI processes.

Open Calls

ORRI Boosters

- Grants of 20,000 €
- 8-month projects
- For beneficiaries already experienced in ORRI

ORRI Incubators

- Grants of 60,000€
- 12-month projects
- For organizations and territories new to ORRI

Call for Evaluators

- Experts with experience in the implementation of ORRI projects and initiatives
- Assist REINFORCING in the evaluation of proposals

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